

Bachelor Thesis

Modeling electron beam dynamics in plasma-lenses after a laser wakefield accelerator

Konrad Schlicke

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First referee

Prof. Dr. Ulrich Schramm

Second referee

Prof. Dr. Thomas E. Cowan

Supervisor

Dr. Richard Pausch

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Abstract

Plasma lenses are a well-established tool for focusing charged particles. This bachelor's thesis investigates the impact of a plasma lens positioned after a laser wakefield acceleration stage, using the particle-in-cell code PIconGPU. This thesis not only focuses on the overall improvement of beam quality but also analyzes the formation of substructures within the beam and their underlying physical causes. The goal is to optimize electron beams for secondary applications such as free-electron lasers (FELs) or plasma wakefield acceleration stages.

Zusammenfassung

Plasmalinsen sind ein bewährtes Mittel zur Fokussierung geladener Teilchen. In dieser Bachelorarbeit wird der Einfluss einer Plasma-Linse nach einer Laser-Wakefield-Beschleunigungsstufe mithilfe des Particle-in-Cell-Codes PIconGPU untersucht. Dabei liegt der Fokus nicht nur auf der globalen Verbesserung der Strahleigenschaften, sondern auch auf der Analyse der entstehenden Substrukturen und deren physikalischen Ursachen. Ziel der Untersuchungen ist die Optimierung von Elektronenstrahlen für sekundäre Anwendungen wie Freie-Elektronen-Laser (FEL) oder Plasma-Wakefield-Beschleunigerstufen.

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1. Introduction: Why is the plasma-lensing effect important?

Laser-plasma accelerators (LPAs) are a rapidly developing technology with the potential to revolutionize particle acceleration. By harnessing the extreme electric fields generated by plasma waves driven by high-intensity laser pulses, LPAs can achieve acceleration gradients exceeding 100 GVm^{-1} [1], several orders of magnitude higher than those achievable with conventional radio-frequency (RF) accelerators. Among LPA techniques, laser wakefield acceleration (LWFA) has proven particularly effective in producing multi-hundred-MeV to GeV-class electron beams over millimeter-scale distances [2, 3].

These high-gradient accelerators open up new possibilities for compact secondary applications, particularly in the development of Free-Electron Lasers (FELs) [4, 5], which require high-brightness beams with low emittance and small transverse size for efficient lasing. Strong and compact focusing elements, such as plasma lenses [6, 7], are therefore essential for transporting and shaping these beams to meet FEL requirements.

At the same time, further progress in accelerator development requires the staging of multiple acceleration units to reach higher energies while maintaining beam quality. A promising approach in this direction is using the electron bunch from the LWFA as driver in a second plasma wakefield accelerator (PWFA) stage. This hybrid LWFA-to-PWFA scheme seeks to combine the compactness of LWFA with the higher efficiency and beam quality preservation of PWFA [8, 9, 10].

A key challenge in both FEL and staging contexts is the transport and refocusing of the electron beam immediately after the LWFA stage. These beams are typically ultra-short and strongly divergent due to space-charge effects and mismatched focusing conditions. Conventional magnetic optics, such as quadrupoles, often lack the focusing strength and compactness required to effectively manipulate these beams. To overcome this limitation, (passive) plasma lenses, regions of tailored plasma density, are employed to refocus the beam using self-generated transverse wakefields within the plasma.

A passive plasma lens [11] can provide symmetric, ultra-strong focusing driven by the beam's own space charge. This mechanism offers a compact and efficient solution for matching LWFA-generated beams both into high-brightness photon sources like FELs and into subsequent PWFA stages for further acceleration.

This thesis focuses on characterizing the focusing properties and beam evolution inside such lenses, as well as identifying the conditions under which a transition from laser-dominated LWFA to the beam-dominated regime, and subsequently to PWFA, can occur [12]. In this thesis, the beam-dominated regime will sometimes be referred to as PWFA.

A deeper understanding of plasma-lensing effects is essential for the development of com-

1. Introduction: Why is the plasma-lensing effect important?

pact, multi-stage accelerators and for the optimization of beam transport toward applications in high-brightness photon sources like FELs.

2. Theoretical introduction to laser plasma accelerators

2.1. Laser-plasma acceleration

Accelerated electron beams play a crucial role in various applications, ranging from fundamental research and medical diagnostics to industrial processes. Most conventional accelerators rely on linear accelerator (linac) technology, where electrons pass through a sequence of radio-frequency (RF) cavities that are synchronized to incrementally increase their energy. However, such systems are limited by the maximum sustainable electric fields, typically between 15 and 75 MVm⁻¹ [13], which necessitates accelerator lengths of several meters to reach energies above 100 MeV.

To achieve higher energies or more compact systems, circular accelerators can be employed. However, these are inefficient for accelerating light particles like electrons, due to substantial energy losses from synchrotron radiation. This motivates the exploration of alternative techniques capable of producing higher acceleration gradients over shorter distances.

A promising advancement in this area is laser-plasma acceleration (LPA). In LPA, a high-intensity, ultrashort laser pulse propagates through a plasma, displacing electrons and generating a trailing plasma wave. This wave, known as a laser wakefield, is analogous to the wake of a boat moving through water. The resulting wakefield acts as a co-propagating acceleration cavity, with electric fields reaching up to 100 GVm⁻¹, several orders of magnitude stronger than in conventional RF cavities. Electrons trapped in this wake can be accelerated to energies of hundreds of MeV within just a few millimeters.

This compact and efficient mechanism holds promise for next-generation, table-top accelerators with applications in high-energy physics [14] and advanced radiation sources [15].

2.1.1. Laser pulse description

In laser wakefield accelerators, a single, short laser pulse with high intensity and a duration typically below 1 ps [1] is used to excite a plasma wave (subsection 2.1.2). To describe such a pulse, both its temporal and spatial characteristics must be considered. A commonly used idealization is the Gaussian beam, a fundamental solution of the paraxial wave equation.

In this framework, the laser pulse is modeled with a Gaussian envelope, which simplifies the analysis of various transverse beam properties. For the purposes of this work, a laser pulse propagating in the y -direction and linearly polarized along the x -axis is considered. The

electric field amplitude is maximal at the beam focus and decreases radially with a Gaussian profile.

The local intensity of the laser correlates with the square of the electric field amplitude. A useful dimensionless parameter to characterize the strength of the laser field is the normalized field strength a_0 , defined as

$$a_0 = \frac{e|\vec{E}|}{m_e c \omega_0}, \quad (2.1)$$

where e is the elementary charge (charge of electron), \vec{E} is the electric field, m_e is the electron mass, c is the speed of light, and ω_0 is the central laser frequency. It is common to specify the peak a_0 value achievable in vacuum to quantify the laser intensity relevant for wakefield acceleration.

2.1.2. Plasma wave excitation and the blowout regime

This section outlines how a laser pulse propagates through plasma, drives electron motion via the ponderomotive force, and sets up a plasma oscillation that eventually forms the accelerating structure.

To drive a plasma wave, a laser pulse propagates through a gas, typically composed of light elements such as hydrogen or helium. The high-intensity laser field ionizes the gas, creating a plasma in which free electrons interact with the oscillating electromagnetic field of the laser.

Due to the Gaussian intensity profile of the laser pulse, the electric field strength varies transversely. As a result, electrons experience a spatially varying force, which, when averaged over an oscillation cycle, is known as the ponderomotive force. For non-relativistic field strengths, this force is given by

$$\vec{F}_p = -\frac{e^2}{4m_e\omega_0^2} \nabla \vec{E}^2. \quad (2.2)$$

The ponderomotive force pushes electrons away from regions of high intensity, driving them forward and transversely out of the laser focus. In contrast, the much heavier protons remain essentially stationary due to their large inertia. This spatial separation of charge creates a positive ion cavity behind the laser pulse (Figure 2.1 a).

As the displaced electrons are pulled back by the restoring force of the ion background, they overshoot their equilibrium positions, initiating a plasma oscillation. This results in the formation of a trailing plasma wave that co-propagates with the laser. The natural frequency of this oscillation is the plasma frequency ω_p , defined as

$$\omega_p = \sqrt{\frac{ne^2}{\epsilon_0 m_e}}, \quad (2.3)$$

where $n = \frac{\text{number of electrons}}{\text{volume}}$ is the plasma density and ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity. The associated wavelength of the plasma wave is the plasma wavelength λ_p , given by

$$\lambda_p = \frac{2\pi c}{\omega_p}. \quad (2.4)$$

When the laser pulse reaches a sufficiently high intensity, characterized by a normalized field strength $a_0 > 4$ [16], the system enters the highly nonlinear blowout or bubble regime. In this regime, the ponderomotive force is strong enough to expel nearly all background

2. Theoretical introduction to laser plasma accelerators

Figure 2.1.: **Top row:** Plasma density and laser intensity, showing the transition from laser-driven to beam-driven wakefields. **Middle row:** Longitudinal electric field E_y at $x = 0$, showing how acceleration shifts from the laser-driven to beam-driven regime. **Bottom row:** Transverse focusing force F_x , highlighting the change in focusing structure and the residual influence of the diffracting laser.

electrons from the vicinity of the laser, forming an ion cavity that is nearly devoid of electrons [17]. This bubble-shaped structure follows the laser pulse and serves as an effective acceleration cavity.

The bubble radius R_b can be approximated as $R_b \approx \lambda_p$, and it depends on both the plasma density and the laser parameters, since $\lambda_p \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$. The cavity length L_b (or longitudinal size) is typically comparable to the radius, $L_b \sim R_b$, resulting in a roughly spherical or ellipsoidal structure in the co-moving frame. The cavity radius scales inversely with the square root of the plasma density, meaning that lower plasma densities lead to larger cavities (Figure 2.1 a-d).

Inside the cavity, the longitudinal electric field E_y responsible for electron acceleration decreases linearly towards the back of the bubble, reaching a minimum near the rear edge (Figure 2.1 e). Additionally, the transverse electric and magnetic fields inside the bubble provide a symmetric linear focusing force toward the propagation axis, beneficial for preserving beam emittance. This causes off-axis relativistic electrons to undergo transverse oscillations, known as betatron oscillations, analogous to motion in a harmonic oscillator [18].

To operate in the blowout regime, not only must the laser intensity be sufficient, but the laser spot size w_0 should approximately match the bubble radius: $w_0 \approx R_b$. This ensures optimal energy transfer and stable bubble formation during propagation [19].

2.1.3. Laser propagation and self-focusing in plasma

For laser-plasma acceleration to be efficient, the laser must maintain a high intensity over a sufficiently long distance. In vacuum, however, a laser beam diffracts according to Gaussian beam optics, and its intensity drops significantly beyond one Rayleigh length from the focus. For example, the peak intensity is reduced by a factor of two just one Rayleigh length away, which limits the effective acceleration length and hence the maximum achievable electron energy.

In plasma, the situation changes dramatically. The plasma modifies the propagation characteristics of the laser beam via nonlinear optical effects, most notably self-focusing if the laser intensity is high enough. This process counteracts diffraction and allows the laser to maintain its intensity over distances much longer than the Rayleigh length in vacuum. As a result, electrons can be accelerated over extended regions, greatly increasing their final energies.

The mechanism of self-focusing can be understood by considering how the plasma refractive index responds to the presence of the intense laser field. The refractive index for an electromagnetic wave in a plasma is given by

$$\eta(r) = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\omega_p^2(r)}{\omega_0^2}}, \quad (2.5)$$

where ω_0 is the laser frequency and $\omega_p(r)$ is the local plasma frequency, which in turn depends on both the local plasma density $n(r)$ and the relativistic mass increase of the electrons due to the laser field.

The intense laser field exerts a ponderomotive force on the electrons, pushing them away from regions of high intensity, typically on the beam axis. This reduces the local plasma density $n(r)$ near the center of the beam. Simultaneously, the laser drives electrons to relativistic speeds, increasing their effective mass and hence the Lorentz factor $\gamma_e(r)$. The local plasma frequency is modified accordingly:

$$\omega_p(r) = \omega_{p,0} \sqrt{\frac{n(r)}{\gamma_e(r)n_0}}, \quad (2.6)$$

where n_0 and $\omega_{p,0}$ are the unperturbed plasma density and frequency, respectively.

Both effects, reduced density $n(r)$ and increased relativistic mass $\gamma_e(r)$, lead to a decrease in $\omega_p(r)$ on-axis, which increases the refractive index $\eta(r)$ near the center. This creates a refractive index profile with a maximum on-axis, resembling a focusing lens. As a result, the beam experiences a net focusing effect [20], enabling it to self-guide through the plasma and sustain wakefield generation over longer distances.

Defocusing in low-density plasma. In the low-density plasma regions used for plasma lensing, self-focusing becomes less effective. This is because the refractive index gradient, which drives focusing, scales with the plasma density. As n reduces, the plasma frequency ω_p also decreases, and the refractive index approaches 1 ($n \rightarrow 1$), as in vacuum. Consequently, the laser no longer experiences significant refractive steering and begins to diffract, leading to defocusing (Figure 2.1 c,d).

This defocusing in the plasma lens stage has two major consequences: first, it reduces the laser's ability to continue driving a strong wakefield, effectively marking the end of LWFA; and second, it shifts the driving mechanism of the plasma wake to the electron bunch itself, initiating a transition to the beam-dominated regime.

This dynamic interplay between self-focusing in plasma and defocusing in less dense plasma is a critical aspect of multi-stage LPA schemes and plays a central role in determining where and how acceleration transitions between laser-dominated and beam-dominated regimes.

2.1.4. Electron injection mechanisms

To utilize the plasma wave for electron acceleration, electrons must first be injected into the accelerating phase of the wakefield. In current LWFA experiments, several injection techniques are commonly employed. The most prominent are wave-breaking injection, density downramp injection, and ionization injection. Each of these mechanisms enables electrons to become trapped inside the plasma wave cavity, where they can be efficiently accelerated.

Ionization injection, the method used in the simulations here, utilizes a doped plasma containing a small fraction of higher- Z atoms, such as nitrogen. These atoms have inner-shell electrons that require significantly higher electric field strengths to ionize. As the laser intensity increases near the focus, these inner electrons are released at a well-defined phase of the plasma wave, allowing them to be injected directly into the cavity. Unlike other electrons, they are ionized inside the wake and thus can be captured more easily.

A key advantage of ionization injection is that it allows for lower laser intensities, while still enabling effective electron trapping [21, 22]. Furthermore, this method offers improved control over beam parameters and has demonstrated favorable results in terms of beam charge and stability [23].

2.1.5. The plasma lens: transition to beam-dominated regime

During the LWFA stage, the high-intensity laser drives the wakefield and electrons are accelerated within the laser-generated bubble. However, as the laser pulse enters a region of reduced plasma density, it begins to diffract and loses its ability to sustain a strong wakefield. This is a result of weakened self-focusing at lower densities, as the refractive index gradient becomes negligible and the beam approaches diffraction-limited behavior. Consequently, the normalized field strength a_0 drops below 1, and the laser can no longer sustain the blowout structure. This transition occurs in plasma density profiles like the one shown in Figure 2.2.

Simultaneously, the relativistic electron bunch produced in the LWFA stage continues to propagate. If it possesses sufficient charge density and duration, it can displace background plasma electrons via its own space charge field, forming a beam-driven wake. This marks the onset of the beam-dominated regime. The two regimes momentarily coexist: the residual laser continues to generate a weak wake while the leading edge of the bunch begins to drive its own wake. This overlap can be seen in Figure 2.1 c.

The longitudinal wakefield in this beam-dominated regime exhibits a quasi-static character in the bunch co-moving frame. As shown in Figure 2.1 h, the accelerating field E_y becomes

dominated by the bunch's profile, with trailing electrons experiencing stronger decelerating forces. Although the overall plasma density is lower, resulting in weaker absolute field strengths, the relative variation of E_y across the bunch length still induces significant energy spread. Particles in the tail of the bunch lose energy more rapidly than those at the front, as they experience stronger plasma response due to their position within the bunch-driven wake.

The transverse wakefield also evolves during the transition from laser-dominated to beam-dominated regime. In the blowout regime of LWFA, the transverse focusing force, generated by the laser-driven wakefield, is highly symmetric and scales with the laser intensity, efficiently guiding electrons toward the axis. As the system transitions into the beam-dominated regime, the focusing force becomes increasingly independent of the laser-driven wakefield, due to laser defocusing. This shift in scaling behavior, from dependence on both laser intensity and plasma density in the laser-dominated regime to dependence on plasma density alone in the beam-dominated regime, is a key characteristic of the transition [11]. This evolution is illustrated in Figure 2.1 i-l, where a reduction in focusing strength is visible. Additionally, residual focusing fields appear outside the bubble, attributed to the weak, diffracted laser pulse.

In the beam-dominated regime, the transverse focusing force experienced by an electron can be approximated as

$$F_r = -\frac{1}{2}m_e\omega_p^2 r \propto -nr, \quad (2.7)$$

where r is the radial displacement from the axis [24]. This expression highlights the linear nature of the focusing field and its dependence on the plasma density n .

This staged transition allows precise tuning of both beam deceleration and focusing conditions. The plasma lens structure not only aids in guiding the bunch but also enables further manipulation of its phase space, energy spread, and transverse emittance, critical aspects for applications in multi-stage accelerator design and beam transport systems.

Figure 2.2.: Plasma density profile used for staged laser-to-beam-driven plasma wakefield acceleration. The orange region between $y = 1 - 3$ mm corresponds to the LWFA plateau, where the plasma density is constant and optimized for laser wakefield acceleration. Beyond $y \approx 4$ mm, the lower-density green region defines the PWFA plateau, where beam-driven wakefields dominate.

2.2. Electron beam properties

The quality of the electron bunch is evaluated by analyzing several key properties derived from its energy and phase-space distributions.

Given the full momentum vector of each particle (from the simulation), $\vec{p} = (p_x, p_y, p_z)^\top$, the kinetic energy of each electron is calculated as

$$E = \sqrt{(m_e c^2)^2 + (pc)^2} - m_e c^2. \quad (2.8)$$

In the energy spectrum of the electron bunch, represented by the differential charge distribution $\frac{dQ}{dE}$, several key parameters can be extracted (Figure 2.3a). These include the maximum of the charge per energy distribution, $\left(\frac{dQ}{dE}\right)_{\max}$ and the corresponding energy, E_{peak} . Because the energy spectrum is not normally distributed, the full width at 50% of the prominence (FWHM) and at 10% of the prominence (FW@10%P) are evaluated separately. Here, the prominence is defined as the vertical distance between the peak and the surrounding baseline. The FWHM characterizes the core width around $\left(\frac{dQ}{dE}\right)_{\max}$, while the FW@10%P includes the extended high-energy tail often associated with self-truncated ionization injection (STII) [25]. The total charge within the FW@10%P region is denoted Q_{tot} , and the charge within the FWHM is denoted Q_{FWHM} . Unless otherwise noted, all subsequent quantities refer to electrons within the FW@10%P window.

Figure 2.3.: Definition of bunch properties: In Figure 2.3a, an exemplary energy spectrum is shown in black. The maximum of the charge per energy distribution $\left(\frac{dQ}{dE}\right)_{\max}$ and the corresponding energy E_{peak} are highlighted in green. The full width at 10% of the prominence is shown in red, with the included charge Q_{tot} in orange. The full width at 50% of the prominence is shown in purple, and the corresponding charge Q_{FWHM} is indicated in blue. In Figure 2.3b, an exemplary charge distribution in transverse phase space is shown.

The divergence of the electron bunch is assessed by defining the transverse deflection angle θ_x as the angle between the transverse momentum p_x and the longitudinal momentum p_y , which aligns with the laser propagation direction:

$$\theta_x = \arctan\left(\frac{p_x}{p_y}\right). \quad (2.9)$$

The beam divergence σ_{θ_x} is defined as the root-mean-square (RMS) spread of the angular charge distribution $\frac{dQ}{d\theta_x}$. The mean angle $\bar{\theta}_x$ is also evaluated to determine whether the bunch deviates from forward propagation.

For the transverse position x , the RMS spread of the charge distribution $\frac{dQ}{dx}$ is defined as σ_x .

In the transverse phase space $\frac{d^2Q}{dx dp_x}$, the distribution shape is analyzed and the occupied area is computed using the normalized emittance ε_n , which is invariant under acceleration. The RMS normalized emittance is calculated from the electron positions x and transverse momenta p_x as the square root of the determinant of the covariance matrix:

$$\varepsilon_n = \sqrt{\begin{vmatrix} \langle x \cdot x \rangle & \langle x \cdot \gamma\beta_x \rangle \\ \langle \gamma\beta_x \cdot x \rangle & \langle \gamma\beta_x \cdot \gamma\beta_x \rangle \end{vmatrix}} \quad \text{with} \quad \gamma\beta_x = \frac{p_x}{m_e c}. \quad (2.10)$$

From this point onward, the transverse phase space $\frac{d^2Q}{dx d\theta_x}$ will be used to gain further insight into the beam structure, as this distribution is also experimentally accessible (Figure 2.3b). A phase space distribution that exhibits an undistorted, elliptical shape will be referred to as *regular*, while any significant deviation from this form will be termed *irregular*.

The primary goal of the plasma lens is to reduce the beam divergence to improve downstream transport, without significantly decreasing Q_{tot} , E_{peak} , or increasing ε_n and FW@10%P. In addition, maintaining a regular phase space structure is crucial for ensuring the beam's suitability for applications such as FELs.

2.3. Modeling with particle-in-cell simulations

2.3.1. Particle-in-Cell simulations for wakefield acceleration

Particle-in-cell (PIC) simulations are a widely used first-principles method for modeling the interaction between charged particles and electromagnetic fields in plasmas. In these simulations, macro-particles, each representing many physical particles, are tracked in continuous space, while the electromagnetic fields are computed on a discrete grid using Maxwell's equations. The particles and fields are coupled through current deposition as well as force calculation.

PIC methods are particularly suited for studying plasma-based acceleration mechanisms such as LWFA and PWFA, where strong field gradients, relativistic effects, and nonlinear plasma dynamics must be resolved self-consistently. These regimes are challenging for fluid or reduced models, making PIC a necessary tool for accurate predictions of wake structure, injection dynamics, and beam quality.

Simulating large numbers of particles interacting via space- and time-dependent electric and magnetic fields comes with significant computational cost. The PIC algorithm solves the problem by discretizing the field equations on a grid and representing the plasma through a reduced number of macro-particles. This reduces computational demands while still capturing essential kinetic effects.

A key advantage of the PIC method is its suitability for parallelization: the simulation domain can be spatially decomposed into independent subregions for distributed field updates, and macro-particles can be advanced independently based on locally interpolated field values. This inherent locality in both field computation and particle motion enables efficient scaling across many processors or GPUs, making large-scale simulations tractable on modern supercomputers.

To perform these simulations the open-source PIC code PIConGPU [26], which is developed at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR) and stands for "particle-in-cell on graphic-compute-units", is used. It implements the full 3D relativistic PIC algorithm and supports a range of additional physics modules relevant for laser- and beam-driven plasma acceleration.

Figure 2.4.: Visualization of the PIC-cycle, illustrating the four main computational steps. The symbols represent the Lorentz force \vec{F} , electric and magnetic fields \vec{E}, \vec{B} , particle position \vec{r} , momentum \vec{p} , charge and current density ρ, \vec{J} . Field updates are computed using FDTD methods on a staggered Yee grid.

The core computational loop of a PIC simulation for a single time step ($n \rightarrow n + 1$) is illustrated in Figure 2.4 and consists of the following steps: First, the electromagnetic fields are interpolated from the grid nodes to the positions of the individual macro-particles. This interpolation allows the computation of the Lorentz force acting on each particle at its exact position. In the next step, each macro-particle is advanced in time by updating its velocity and position according to this interpolated force, based on the equations of motion. After the macro-particles have moved, their new positions and velocities are used to deposit current densities back onto the grid. Finally, this updated source information is used to calculate the electromagnetic fields on the simulation grid by solving Maxwell's equations with the help of one of the various finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) methods. In this approach, the spatial and temporal derivatives in Maxwell's equations are approximated using centered finite differences. As a consequence, the electric and magnetic field components are not evaluated at the same positions in space or time. Instead, they are placed on a staggered Yee grid (Figure 2.5a), where electric and magnetic field components are offset by half a grid cell in space and half a time step in time. Diagnostics are applied at the end of each time step to extract data. This PIC-cycle is repeated multiple times for longer simulation durations.

To make the simulation of laser- or beam-driven wakefield acceleration feasible, PIC codes typically use a co-moving simulation window that follows the laser pulse and accelerated electrons at the speed of light. This approach limits the simulated region to the vicinity of interest, typically around the accelerating structure, thereby avoiding the need to compute the full plasma volume and drastically reducing the number of particles and grid points that must be tracked. The size of the window in the transverse directions (x and z) is chosen to comfortably fit the cavity structure, ensuring it remains fully contained throughout the simulation, even as the plasma density decreases in the plasma lens. In the propagation direction y , the length of the simulation box is selected such that the laser, the driven electrons, and the full cavity in the LWFA stage fit within the window. However, in the lower density region, where the cavity becomes significantly longer, only the front part of the cavity with the electron bunch fits inside the simulation box (Figure 2.1 a-c). Since the electrons move at approximately the speed of light (for $E > 100$ MeV $\Rightarrow v > 0.9998c$), the information from the

back of the cavity does not affect the particles being tracked in the simulation. This allows for the exclusion of the longer cavity regions in the lower-density plasma without impacting the accuracy of the simulation, thus saving significant computational resources.

2.3.2. Field interpolation and Lorentz force calculation on a Yee grid

Figure 2.5.: Staggered field component layout in the Yee grid (left) and schematic of the required linear interpolation in the transverse plane (right) to ensure spatial alignment for accurate Lorentz force calculations.

Figure 2.6.: Effect of field interpolation on the focusing force F_x at an example position. The left plot (no interpolation) shows significant artifacts near $y = 5.415$ mm, while the right plot (with interpolation) yields a smoother and more physically accurate result.

The transition from laser-dominated to beam-dominated wakefield acceleration ([subsection 2.1.5](#)) is investigated by analyzing the focusing force acting on the electrons. At energies above 100 MeV, relativistic electrons can be approximated to move at the speed of light c in the propagation direction y , simplifying the Lorentz force to:

$$\vec{F} = q(\vec{E} + \vec{v} \times \vec{B}) \approx -e(\vec{E} + c \hat{e}_y \times \vec{B}), \quad (2.11)$$

where \hat{e}_y denotes the unit vector in the propagation direction. The resulting force components become:

$$F_x = -e(E_x - cB_z), \quad (2.12)$$

$$F_z = e(E_z - cB_x). \quad (2.13)$$

Since the electric and magnetic field components in the simulation are defined on a staggered Yee grid (Figure 2.5a), direct addition without correcting for spatial offsets introduces significant error. To address this, linear interpolation is applied to align the fields spatially before computing the Lorentz force. For example, although E_x and B_z lie in the same xy -plane, B_z is offset by half a cell in the y -direction (Figure 2.5b). Therefore, B_z is interpolated to the same y -coordinate as E_x to ensure consistent force evaluation. The improvement achieved through interpolation is demonstrated in Figure 2.6. Without interpolation (left), the calculated F_x exhibits unphysical artifacts around $y = 5.415$ mm. With interpolation (right), these artifacts are removed, resulting in a more accurate and smooth field profile.

2.3.3. Termination criteria

In some cases, especially those involving flat plateau profiles, the simulations were deliberately terminated before reaching the full propagation length. This was done to avoid unnecessary computational expenses once it became clear that (i) the electron bunch had already lost a significant amount of energy or charge, (ii) the bunch had expanded beyond the simulation boundaries, or (iii) no further meaningful evolution in beam parameters was expected. As a result, not all plotted curves extend to the same final propagation distance y .

3. Analysis of electron bunch dynamics in various plasma lens profiles

3.1. Density profiles

This section analyzes various plasma density profiles to improve the electron beam properties outlined at the end of [section 2.2](#). Each profile defines the plasma density as $n = \frac{\text{number of electrons}}{\text{volume}}$. The simulations are based on a realistic experimental setup for the LWFA stage, adapted from [25], with modifications applied only to the plasma lens structure for $y > 4$ mm. An overview of all profiles and their key characteristics is provided in [Table 3.1](#), serving as a reference for the analyses that follow. The corresponding analytical expressions and parameters for each profile type (p ... plateau, dip ... dip followed by plateau, f ... Gaussian falloff, and dip+f ... dip followed by Gaussian falloff) are provided in [Appendix A](#). The impact of each profile on the electron beam properties is discussed in detail in the subsequent subsections.

3. Analysis of electron bunch dynamics in various plasma lens profiles

Table 3.1.: Summary of simulated plasma density profiles used in the plasma lens study. The profiles are grouped by type (p ... plateau, dip ... dip followed by plateau, f ... Gaussian falloff, and dip+f ... dip followed by Gaussian falloff) and characterized by their key beam dynamics. Analytical expressions and parameters for each profile are provided in [Appendix A](#).

name	profile	$\frac{h_p}{10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}}$	$\frac{\sigma_{\text{end}}}{\text{mm}}$	key characteristics
$n_{p,1}$ $n_{p,2}$ $n_{p,3}$ $n_{p,4}$		38 19 9.5 3.8	—	high energy loss at large h_p , irregular phase space and emittance increase at low h_p , no further improvement beyond initial plateau (after $y = 5 \text{ mm}$)
n_{dip}		9.5	—	worst transverse phase space structure, broadening of $\frac{dQ}{d\theta_x}$ peak
$n_{f,1}$ $n_{f,2}$ $n_{f,3}$ $n_{f,4}$		7.6	4.5 3.0 1.5 0.3	further divergence reduction in the Gaussian falloff, increased spectral width for longer falloffs, best balance between focusing and energy loss for profile $n_{f,3}$
$n_{\text{dip+f}}$		7.6	1.5	increased emittance due to irregular phase space; divergence reduction in the Gaussian falloff, but less than n_f profiles

3.1.1. Plateau profiles

To understand the effect of a constant plasma density on the electron bunch, the evolution of the transverse phase space was analyzed. As the electron bunch enters the plateau section, it begins to expand transversely due to the reduced focusing force (subsection 2.1.5). Particles with higher transverse deflection angles θ_x move outward more rapidly, creating a structure in which lower- θ_x electrons remain near the beam axis, while higher- θ_x electrons occupy the periphery (Figure 3.1 b).

Figure 3.1.: Illustration of the transverse oscillation behavior for the plasma density profile $n_{p,3}$. (a) shows the longitudinal plasma density $n(y)$. (b)-(d) present the transverse angle θ_x and the corresponding focusing force F_x in the xy -plane of the electron bunch, highlighting the evolution of betatron motion within the density profile.

For moderately low-density plateaus, the resulting weaker focusing force from the expanded plasma cavity is still sufficient to redirect most electrons back toward the transverse center. As they are pulled inward, they gain transverse momentum and an increase in θ_x (Figure 3.1 c). Many of these particles then continue outward on the opposite side of the axis, entering a new phase of transverse expansion (Figure 3.1 d). Upon approaching the cavity boundaries again, they encounter stronger focusing fields, are decelerated, and reverse direction (Figure 3.1 e).

Due to the weak residual laser-generated fields, even electrons outside the beam-driven cavity experience a mild focusing force in the surrounding region shaped by the expanded laser profile (subsection 2.1.5). While much weaker than the focusing inside the cavity, this broader field still slightly reduces their transverse momentum, slowing their outward drift over time.

While individual particles experience different focusing strengths and have varying transverse momenta, resulting in a range of oscillation amplitudes and phases, the collective beam properties still exhibit an overall oscillatory pattern. The transverse beam size σ_x reaches a minimum when the bunch is most concentrated near the axis and a maximum when the distribution is widest during outward motion. Conversely, the beam divergence σ_{θ_x}

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peaks when many electrons are near the axis with high transverse momentum, and drops when they are spread out but moving more slowly.

Because electrons at the front of the bunch experience weaker focusing forces, they expand wider than those in the rear (Figure 3.1c–d). This leads to a subtle front-rear asymmetry in the beam’s evolution, which develops slowly and results in a gradual increase in emittance.

If the focusing force is too weak to trap a majority of the electrons, as in the case of the lowest plateau $n_{p,4}$, the bunch separates: inner particles with sufficiently low θ_x remain confined and undergo the aforementioned oscillatory dynamics, while a substantial portion of higher- θ_x electrons escape the cavity. These outer particles continue expanding, though they too gradually lose transverse momentum under the weak laser-driven focusing force.

This evolution results in a cross-shaped transverse phase space distribution (Figure 3.2d), which deviates significantly from the regular elliptical shape defined in section 2.2. The confined inner electrons form the vertical axis of the cross, while the outward-drifting particles form the horizontal component.

Figure 3.2.: Deformation of the transverse phase space for the plasma density profile $n_{p,4}$. (a) shows the plasma density $n(y)$, while (b)–(d) depict the transverse phase space at different propagation distances y . Ellipses highlight the two components of the electron bunch to illustrate the change in the phase space distribution.

With this mechanism in mind, the evolution of the beam properties in plasma lenses with different plateau heights (Figure 3.3a) can be better understood.

For the profiles $n_{p,2}$, and particularly $n_{p,1}$, the electron bunch loses energy too rapidly (Figure 3.3b), due to higher densities resulting in strong fields (subsection 2.1.5). In contrast, for the lowest-density case $n_{p,4}$, a strong increase in normalized emittance ϵ_n is observed (Figure 3.3c), accompanied by the formation of an irregular transverse phase space structure. This is attributed to the significantly reduced focusing force in the low-density plasma.

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The plateau height of $n_{p,3}$ represents a compromise between the energy loss encountered at higher plasma densities and the emittance growth observed at lower ones. However, the beam divergence no longer decreases substantially beyond the initial plateau region, apart from minor oscillations around 3 mrad (Figure 3.3d). Meanwhile, the electron bunch continues to lose energy (Figure 3.3b) and exhibits growing normalized emittance due to its transverse expansion in the x-direction (Figure 3.3c). This motivates the investigation of Gaussian falloff profiles presented in subsection 3.1.3, which aim to further optimize the bunch properties beyond the plateau.

Figure 3.3.: Evolution of bunch properties over propagation distance y for plasma densities $n_{p,i}$ with a plateau in the down ramp.

3.1.2. Constant profile with dip

To better reflect experimental conditions, a density profile featuring an initial dip was investigated. This dip mimics the density depression observed when using a guiding structure, such as a wedge, to shape the gas flow from a nozzle and form a passive plasma lens [11]. In such a configuration, the deformation of the transverse phase space becomes even more pronounced than in the case of the lowest plateau profile $n_{p,4}$. Initially, the bunch expands as it traverses the low-density region. When the plasma density increases again, the cavity narrows (subsection 2.1.2) and the focusing force intensifies. This results in a stronger decoupling between confined inner and outward-drifting electrons (as described in subsection 3.1.1), as the inner electrons gain significant transverse momentum. This, in turn, leads to a strongly distorted phase space (Figure 3.4d). The irregular structure is accompanied

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Figure 3.4.: Deformation of the transverse phase space for a plasma density profile with a plateau height of $h_p = 9.5 \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-3}$ and a dip. (a) shows the plasma density $n(y)$, while (b)-(d) depict the transverse phase space at different propagation distances y . The green lines show the charge distribution as a function of transverse deflection angle θ_x .

by a renewed increase in normalized emittance. These findings suggest that while the experimental results are promising, they could be further improved by minimizing the initial density dip. This would help preserve the beam's transverse phase space structure and reduce the broadening of the $\frac{dQ}{d\theta_x}$ peak, as shown in Figure 3.4.

3.1.3. Gaussian falloff profiles

To improve the bunch properties beyond the initial plateau section, Gaussian-shaped down ramps with varying standard deviations σ_{end} were simulated, all starting from a fixed density of $7.6 \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-3}$ (Figure 3.5a). This initial plateau height was selected based on prior observations from the plateau profiles: it offers a compromise that limits energy loss while maintaining a sufficiently strong focusing force to preserve a regular, approximately elliptical transverse phase space structure.

Note that in some of the following figures, such as Figure 3.5d, a binned diagnostic was used to compute beam properties at finer resolution along the propagation axis y . This method requires significantly less memory than full particle tracking, allowing more frequent sampling and resulting in smoother curves compared to other quantities, such as σ_x .

All profiles $n_{f,i}$ show a reduction in divergence beyond the initial plateau (Figure 3.5d). The case $n_{f,3}$ exhibits the lowest final divergence, reaching approximately 1.7 mrad, while the others approach 2 mrad at $y = 14.77$ mm. Notably, even in the residual density region beyond $y = 10$ mm, where the plasma density drops to $0.38 \times 10^{16} \text{cm}^{-3}$, the $n_{f,3}$ profile

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Figure 3.5.: Evolution of bunch properties over propagation distance y for plasma densities $n_{f,i}$, each featuring a plateau followed by a Gaussian falloff in the down ramp.

continues to exhibit a decline in divergence (Figure 3.5d), highlighting the sustained influence of weak focusing forces. The phase space oscillations described earlier (subsection 3.1.1) are also apparent in the divergence curves $\sigma_{\theta_x}(y)$, with the number of cycles depending on how quickly the density drops to a level where such motion ceases. As expected, steeper ramps result in fewer periods, although their frequency remains nearly constant across all cases. These oscillations are consistent with betatron oscillations, as described in subsection 2.1.2.

At the front of the electron bunch, the beam expands transversely in x with low divergence (Figure 3.6b), as it experiences minimal focusing forces from the wakefield cavity (Figure 3.1 b-d). Electrons further back along the bunch experience stronger focusing forces, causing them to undergo transverse betatron motion that contributes to the oscillatory pattern seen in the overall divergence σ_{θ_x} (Figure 3.6a). The frequency of this transverse motion changes along the bunch length because the focusing force increases toward the rear. Meanwhile, the increase in the transverse beam size σ_x (Figure 3.5c) mainly originates from the spreading of electrons at the front of the bunch, which do not oscillate as explained above. As the plasma density drops at larger propagation distances y , the focusing forces weaken and the oscillations throughout the bunch gradually end (Figure 3.6b).

For these decreasing density profiles, the divergence continues to drop while the bunch simultaneously expands transversely as it undergoes the oscillations. This behavior appears to be caused by the gradually weakening focusing forces in the down ramp. In contrast, such damping is not observed in the plateau profiles (Figure 3.3d).

The emittance growth is also significantly reduced for the Gaussian falloffs, which is a

Figure 3.6.: Evolution of the electron beam divergence σ_{θ_x} during propagation for the Gaussian falloff density profile $n_{f,1}$. (a) shows the overall beam divergence as a function of propagation distance y . (b) displays the divergence resolved by longitudinal position within the bunch, expressed as $y-ct$, as it evolves over the propagation distance y . (c) presents the longitudinal charge distribution $\frac{dQ}{d(y-ct)}$ in green, also mapped as a function of propagation distance y , illustrating the beam's temporal structure.

favorable result, particularly for applications such as FELs (Figure 3.5b). In profiles $n_{f,1}$ and $n_{f,2}$, small oscillations in $\epsilon_r(y)$ are observed, indicating mild phase space deformation linked to the transverse oscillations, though far less pronounced than in all previous cases. The evolution of the transverse spread σ_x is shown in Figure 3.5c. As expected, shorter falloffs result in faster growth of σ_x , since the weaker focusing force at lower densities is less effective at containing the bunch.

The evaluation method applied throughout this work uses the same filter criteria (selecting electrons within the FW@10%P energy window; see section 2.2) at every output step, as if the bunch were extracted at that position in a staged setup. This means that the tracked particle population may differ from step to step, and thus physical conservation laws (e.g., Liouville's theorem) do not necessarily apply to the evolving distribution. Consequently, effects such as emittance growth or a linear increase in transverse beam size, despite a concurrent reduction in divergence, can appear, as seen for example in the $n_{f,3}$ case.

In the next part, the front and rear of the electron bunch will refer to the positions of the electrons in longitudinal direction (y -direction).

Note that for all energy-related quantities shown in the following figures, the binned diagnostic used has an energy resolution of 1 MeV. As a result, spectral quantities such as E_{peak} and the charge contained in a specific energy window (Q_{FWHM} , Q_{tot}) exhibit step-like patterns due to the finite bin width.

The evolution of the energy spectrum peak position reveals a faster energy decrease for profiles with longer falloffs (Figure 3.7a). This occurs because these profiles remain at higher plasma densities for longer propagation distances. However, instead of a smooth decrease, the energy peak position exhibits noticeable jumps. These discontinuities arise due to the presence of multiple distinct electron populations, which originate from K-shell ionization of

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Figure 3.7.: Evolution of the energy spectrum over propagation distance y for plasma densities $n_{f,i}$, each featuring a plateau followed by a Gaussian falloff in the down ramp.

nitrogen during STII injection [25]. Since these populations are injected at different longitudinal positions, they experience different energy loss rates during propagation. In particular, the electrons at the rear of the bunch lose energy more rapidly, while the front remains relatively unaffected (subsection 2.1.5). As a result, the energy spectrum develops multiple sub-peaks, causing the main peak location to jump irregularly (Figure 3.8a).

This evolution also affects the spectral width. The FW@10%P remains mostly unchanged across these jumps (Figure 3.7b), indicating that the dominant energy peak is relatively stable, though its structure may include multiple nearby peaks. The FWHM, on the other hand, shows a more pronounced shift (Figure 3.7c). This is attributed to the transformation of the energy spectrum from a single-peaked distribution with a pronounced high-energy tail (Figure 3.8b), to a broader distribution where multiple longitudinal segments overlap in energy (Figure 3.8c).

The longer falloff cases $n_{f,1}$ and $n_{f,2}$ show a clear increase in FW@10%P after 8 mm. This indicates a redistribution of spectral charge as the rear part of the bunch loses energy more rapidly than the front. Initially, the rear of the bunch formed the high-energy tail of the spec-

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Figure 3.8.: Evolution of the $\frac{dQ}{dE}$ spectrum for the plasma density profile $n_{f,2}$. (a) shows the charge per energy distribution $\frac{dQ}{dE}(y)$, while (b)-(d) depict the differential distribution $\frac{d^2Q}{dE dy}$. Green lines indicate the corresponding $\frac{dQ}{dE}$ spectra at selected propagation distances y . Black dotted lines mark the energy E_{peak} corresponding to the peak of $\frac{dQ}{dE}$, and blue shaded regions represent the charge contained within the FWHM Q_{FWHM} . In (c) and (d), the energy distortion around 272 MeV is also visible (subsection 3.2.2).

trum (Figure 3.8b). As these electrons lose energy and the front remains largely unaffected, the energy distribution shifts: the former tail diminishes, and the front in longitudinal direction y now becomes the new forefront part of the spectrum (Figure 3.8d). This new structure also explains the concurrent rise in the relative energy spread $\frac{\text{FW@10\%P}}{E_{\text{peak}}}$ for these cases, which deviates from the flatter behavior seen in $n_{f,3}$ and $n_{f,4}$, which stabilize around 35% (Figure 3.7d).

For $n_{f,3}$, the relative energy spread based on the FWHM, $\frac{\text{FWHM}}{E_{\text{peak}}}$, reaches approximately 30% (Figure 3.7e) as the front and rear segments of the bunch begin to overlap in the energy distribution. The similarity between the FWHM and FW@10%P in this case indicates a more compact energy spectrum. This suggests that the bunch charge is more centrally concentrated in energy, with fewer outliers or spectral tails. A corresponding trend can be seen in the convergence of the total bunch charge Q_{tot} (Figure 3.7f) and the FWHM charge Q_{FWHM} (Figure 3.7g), implying that most of the charge lies within the main spectral peak (Figure 3.9a). The energy spectrum develops a main peak with three distinct local maxima of comparable height (Figure 3.9a), which explains the multiple small jumps observed in E_{peak} (Figure 3.7a).

In contrast, for the shortest falloff $n_{f,4}$, the energy loss is insufficient to significantly overlap the front and rear segments of the bunch. As a result, the FWHM remains more stable, and

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Figure 3.9.: Energy distribution $\frac{dQ}{dE}$ for two profiles with Gaussian falloff. The blue shaded area indicates the charge within the FWHM, Q_{FWHM} , and the orange shaded area shows the charge within the FW@10%P, $Q_{FW@10\%}$.

the spectrum shape evolves less dramatically, with the high-energy tail persisting throughout ([Figure 3.9b](#)).

The total bunch charge Q_{tot} decreases more for longer falloffs, as these stay in the denser plasma regions longer, leading to greater energy loss and eventual particle loss ([Figure 3.7f](#)). The charge within the FWHM energy window, Q_{FWHM} , initially increases for all cases due to the growing overlap between front and rear bunch segments, which broadens the FWHM. However, for $n_{f,1}$ and $n_{f,2}$, this value subsequently decreases a lot after $y \approx 7.5$ mm as electrons from the far rear of the bunch drop below the main energy peak and are effectively lost.

Figure 3.10.: Evolution of the maximum charge density over propagation distance y for plasma density profiles $n_{f,i}$. (a) shows the peak of the charge per energy distribution, $\left(\frac{dQ}{dE}\right)_{max}$, while (b) depicts the peak of the charge per energy and divergence angle, $\left(\frac{d^2Q}{dE d\theta_x}\right)_{max}$.

From an FEL perspective, it is particularly useful to consider the peak charge per energy

$\left(\frac{dQ}{dE}\right)_{\max}$, as it directly relates to the spectral brightness and coherence of the emitted radiation. A general decrease in this quantity is observed across all profiles (Figure 3.10a), primarily due to energy spreading resulting from differential energy loss along the bunch. However, shorter falloff profiles retain higher peak values, as they experience less longitudinal energy separation and thus preserve a more concentrated spectral charge distribution.

Complementary to this, $\left(\frac{d^2Q}{dE d\theta_x}\right)_{\max}$ accounts for both energy and angular spread, providing a more complete picture of the beam's spectral-brilliance potential. It partially captures the transverse phase space oscillations described in subsection 3.1.3. Notably, for the $n_{f,3}$ case, a later increase in $\left(\frac{d^2Q}{dE d\theta_x}\right)_{\max}$ is observed (Figure 3.10b), driven by a reduction in beam divergence. This is a promising result, indicating improved beam quality despite some energy loss. After $y = 10$ mm, the profile $n_{f,2}$ exhibits a higher value of $\left(\frac{d^2Q}{dE d\theta_x}\right)_{\max}$ compared to $n_{f,1}$, primarily due to its lower beam divergence. This difference arises because $n_{f,1}$ undergoes an additional oscillation cycle beyond this point (Figure 3.5d). Other electron beam properties remain similar between these two profiles.

3.1.4. Gaussian falloff profile with dip

To better align with experimentally observed density profiles, a configuration combining the initial dip (as discussed in subsection 3.1.2) with the most favorable Gaussian falloff ($\sigma_{\text{end}} = 1.5$ mm) from subsection 3.1.3 was simulated (Figure 3.11a).

Figure 3.11.: Evolution of bunch properties over propagation distance y for the plasma density profiles $n_{f,3}$, which features a plateau followed by a Gaussian falloff, and $n_{\text{dip+f}}$, which includes an initial dip followed by the same Gaussian falloff.

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Identically to subsection 3.1.1, the splitting of the transverse phase space into inner and outer electron populations results in a broader transverse beam size (Figure 3.11c). For the $n_{\text{dip+f}}$ profile, this manifests between $y = 4\text{--}8$ mm, where the outer electrons expand more significantly than in the $n_{f,3}$ case.

Electrons from the inner population gain transverse momentum at the end of the dip (Figure 3.11b), which reduces the effectiveness of subsequent focusing. This results in faster beam expansion beyond $y = 11$ mm (Figure 3.11c), and leads to a $\sim 49\%$ higher final divergence compared to $n_{f,3}$ (Figure 3.11d).

The emittance increases due to this phase space distortion and only slightly decreases when the inner and outer components partially overlap as the phase space ellipse of the inner electrons rotates (Figure 3.12). However, the normalized emittance remains significantly higher than in the case without a dip (Figure 3.11b).

Figure 3.12.: Evolution of the transverse phase space after the dip for the plasma density profile $n_{\text{dip+f}}$, which combines an initial dip with a Gaussian falloff. (a) shows the plasma density $n(y)$, while (b)–(d) depict the transverse phase space at selected propagation distances y . The green lines indicate the charge distribution as a function of transverse deflection angle θ_x .

Compared to the plateau with dip profile discussed in subsection 3.1.2, the combination with a Gaussian falloff partially mitigates the negative effects of the initial dip. While the transverse phase space still splits into inner and outer components, the tailored density decrease after the dip helps reduce divergence to some extent, due to the gradually weakening focusing forces. Additionally, the reduced energy loss compared to higher-density plateau configurations is another advantage of this profile.

To optimize profiles with dips, it would be necessary to evaluate which density shapes are experimentally possible, for example via hydrodynamic simulations.

3.1.5. Experimental implications for plasma lens shaping

Based on the simulation results presented in the preceding sections, several practical recommendations can be made for designing plasma lenses in experimental setups.

First, the initial plasma density after the LWFA stage should be chosen carefully to balance energy loss at higher densities against emittance growth caused by irregular phase space structures at lower densities (subsection 3.1.1).

Second, the initial dip in the density profile, often introduced by wedge-shaped structures for gas flow control, should be minimized or carefully controlled. As shown in subsection 3.1.2, such dips can lead to irregular phase space evolution and increased emittance, which are unfavorable to beam quality. Additionally, the dip reduces the overall focusing effectiveness of the lens, as it limits the extent to which divergence can be decreased compared to the dip-free case (subsection 3.1.4).

Third, density profiles with a gradual Gaussian falloff, such as $n_{f,3}$ (Figure 3.5a), were found to offer an excellent compromise between minimizing energy loss and reducing divergence. However, not all smooth transitions are equally effective: the shape and steepness of the falloff must be carefully optimized to ensure adequate focusing while avoiding excessive spectral broadening.

Therefore, for optimal beam transport and potential applications in FELs or subsequent PWFA stages, experimentalists are encouraged to implement plasma lenses with an optimized tapering shape of the density profile.

3.2. Numerical considerations and artifacts

3.2.1. Transverse beam drift and boundary conditions

In all simulations, after $y = 9$ mm, the bunch unexpectedly begins to drift from the transverse center $z = 0$, as shown in Figure 3.13a.

(a) Mean transverse z -position of the bunch for varying simulation box widths (given in cells) and boundary conditions (PML and 'exp', where 'exp' denotes exponential damping). A consistent drift emerges when insufficient absorption leads to spurious transverse fields.

(b) Maximum normalized field strength $a_{0,\text{max}}$ as a function of propagation distance y for different simulation box widths and boundary conditions. For exponential damping, a late-stage increase in $a_{0,\text{max}}$ is observed, attributed to the buildup of standing-wave-like patterns.

Figure 3.13.: Numerical artifact affecting beam propagation. Subfigure (a) shows a transverse drift of the bunch and (b) reveals anomalous laser intensity behavior due to boundary condition effects.

Increasing the transverse width of the simulation box from 848 to 1024 cells (i.e., from $150.27 \mu\text{m}$ to $181.45 \mu\text{m}$) delays the onset of the transverse drift to $y = 12$ mm. This behavior suggests that the laser field may not be sufficiently absorbed at the simulation boundaries. As the laser propagates and expands transversely, inadequate absorption can lead to the formation of non-physical, standing-wave-like fields. These fields can eventually impose asymmetric transverse forces on the electron bunch, resulting in the observed deflection.

To investigate this further, the boundary conditions for field absorption were changed from a Perfectly Matched Layer (PML) with 12-cell thickness to an exponential damping absorber with a thickness of 32 cells. Under these modified conditions, the bunch retained forward propagation (Figure 3.13a), even though the laser formed an even stronger standing-wave-like pattern (Figure 3.14b). However, the updated absorber produced a pattern that appeared symmetric about the $z = 0$ axis (Figure 3.14c,d), mitigating the net transverse force on the bunch. This suggests that the original PML implementation did not provide a sufficiently smooth absorption profile, leading to spurious reflections due to the discretization of the wave equation.

Although this deviation only becomes apparent at very late stages, the maximum offset observed, for the PML case with a width of 848 cells, is less than three wavelengths over a propagation distance of 4 mm. While this has minimal impact on the interpretation of the present results, it should be taken into account for future simulations, particularly in scenarios where precise transverse stability is critical.

Figure 3.14.: Comparison of the normalized field strength a_0 at $y = 14.8$ mm using two different boundary conditions: PML and an exponential absorbing layer. The first row ((a) and (b)) shows the envelope of a_0 in the yz -plane. The second row ((c) and (d)) depicts the corresponding transverse symmetry, quantified by the difference Δa_0 between the envelope and its mirrored counterpart across the y -axis at $z = 0$.

3.2.2. Analysis of an artifact in the energy spectrum

A numerical artifact was found around 272 MeV, where electrons just below this energy appear to be insufficiently pushed in the simulation, causing them to lag behind slightly in the propagation direction. These delayed particles drift toward the rear of the bunch, entering regions of stronger decelerating fields and losing more energy as a result. This process results in the formation of an artificial gap in the energy spectrum, an abrupt cut at 272 MeV, with a noticeable underrepresentation of electrons below that threshold (Figure 3.15). Importantly, this artifact is not caused by particles leaving the simulation window or by boundary interactions, as the affected electrons remain well within the simulation box and are not located near any borders. It is also unclear why not all electrons at this specific energy are affected equally along the longitudinal direction, given that the longitudinal extent of the bunch is consistent across all energy levels. The artifact does not appear at the start

Figure 3.15.: Electron density in energy-position space, $\frac{d^2Q}{dy dE}$, showing a distinct gap at 272 MeV. In green the corresponding $\frac{dQ}{dE}$ spectrum also has a sharp edge at this value. Particles just below this energy exhibit a sharp density drop, indicating a numerical artifact: affected electrons are insufficiently accelerated, causing them to lag in position and shift toward regions of stronger decelerating fields, resulting in further energy loss. This creates a visible discontinuity in the otherwise smooth energy distribution.

but emerges after a certain propagation distance and then reappears either periodically, progressively, or both.

Because the effect is confined to a narrow energy band, other beam metrics such as emittance and divergence remain reliable. However, the distortion in the energy distribution should be acknowledged in any spectral interpretation.

4. Summary and outlook

This thesis investigated the passive plasma-lensing effect following a LWFA stage using fully relativistic particle-in-cell simulations with the PIconGPU code. The focus was placed on understanding the beam dynamics within the lens and identifying conditions that support effective focusing.

A variety of tailored plasma density profiles were explored, including plateaus and Gaussian falloff ramps. Additionally, initial density dips were considered for both types of plasma lenses. The results demonstrate that Gaussian falloff profiles can significantly reduce beam divergence while maintaining favorable emittance and energy spread characteristics. In particular, the profile $n_{f,3}$ (Figure 3.5a) showed the most promising behavior, achieving strong focusing with moderate energy loss and minimal spectral broadening.

Furthermore, the location at which the electron bunch is extracted from the LWFA stage and transferred to the next stage, such as a PWFA stage, can be critical. Due to ongoing phase space rotation in the residual background plasma, the beam's divergence oscillates during propagation (Figure 3.5d). These oscillations are caused by weak but non-negligible focusing fields originating from the beam-driven wakefield of the electron bunch itself. If the beam is coupled into the next stage during a phase of high divergence, its quality will suffer. In contrast, synchronizing the extraction point with a moment of minimal divergence yields better beam quality and more efficient transport.

Additionally, key spectral and phase-space properties were evaluated, including transverse emittance, energy spread (FWHM and FW@10%P), and the peak charge densities $\left(\frac{dQ}{dE}\right)_{\max}$ and $\left(\frac{d^2Q}{dE d\theta_x}\right)_{\max}$. The simulations suggest that a well-designed plasma lens can preserve or even enhance beam-quality in a compact setup. This is relevant for applications such as FELs, where beam brightness and spectral quality are critical, but it also offers a path toward scalable, all-optical multi-stage accelerator concepts.

Future work could extend these studies by evaluating the robustness of lensing under experimental imperfections, optimizing plasma density profiles for specific electron beam properties, and exploring active plasma lensing strategies [28]. Such active lenses could provide tunable, symmetric focusing fields that are less sensitive to fluctuations in the incoming bunch, enabling more consistent and adaptable beam transport.

Moreover, experimental validation of the identified optimal density profiles would be a valuable next step to bridge the gap between simulation, experiment and application. The results presented here can help guide the design of compact lensing sections in high-brightness FEL injectors or staged LWFA-PWFA systems.

A. Appendix: analytical density profiles

The Gaussian function is defined as:

$$g(y, \mu, \sigma) = \exp\left(-\frac{(y - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

with the center of the Gaussian function μ and the width (standard deviation) σ .

Parameters of the density profile:

$\sigma = 0.3 \text{ mm}$	(width of up- and downramp of LWFA plateau)
$y_1 = 1.2 \text{ mm}$	(start of LWFA plateau)
$y_2 = 2.9 \text{ mm}$	(end of LWFA plateau)
$h_{\text{LWFA}} = 3.3 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$	(height of the LWFA plateau)
h_p	(height of the plasma lens plateau)

The equation for the density profile with **plateau** is:

$$n_p(y) = \begin{cases} h_{\text{LWFA}} \cdot g(y, y_1, \sigma) & \text{if } y \leq y_1 \\ h_{\text{LWFA}} & \text{if } y_1 < y \leq y_2 \\ (h_{\text{LWFA}} - h_p) \cdot g(y, y_2, \sigma) + h_p & \text{if } y > y_2 \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Additional parameters for density profile **with a dip**:

$\sigma_{\text{dip}} = 0.75 \text{ mm}$	(width of upramp from dip)
$y_{\text{d1}} = 4.4 \text{ mm}$	(start of dip)
$y_{\text{d2}} = 5.96 \text{ mm}$	(end of dip)
$h_d = 2.85 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$	(height of dip)

The equation for the density profile with a dip is:

$$n_{\text{dip}}(y) = \begin{cases} h_{\text{LWFA}} \cdot g(y, y_1, \sigma) & \text{if } y \leq y_1 \\ h_{\text{LWFA}} & \text{if } y_1 < y \leq y_2 \\ (h_{\text{LWFA}} - h_d) \cdot g(y, y_2, \sigma) + h_d & \text{if } y_2 < y \leq y_{\text{d1}} \\ (h_p - h_d) \cdot g(y, y_{\text{d2}}, \sigma_{\text{dip}}) + h_d & \text{if } y_{\text{d1}} < y \leq y_{\text{d2}} \\ h_p & \text{if } y > y_{\text{d2}} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Additional parameters for density profile with **Gaussian falloff**:

σ_{end}	width of Gaussian falloff
$y_{\text{end}} = 5 \text{ mm}$	start of Gaussian falloff
$h_{\text{end}} = 0.38 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$	residual density after Gaussian falloff

The equation for the density profiles with Gaussian falloff:

$$n_f(y) = \begin{cases} h_{\text{LWFA}} \cdot g(y, y_1, \sigma) & \text{if } y \leq y_1 \\ h_{\text{LWFA}} & \text{if } y_1 < y \leq y_2 \\ (h_{\text{LWFA}} - h_p) \cdot g(y, y_2, \sigma) + h_p & \text{if } y_2 < y \leq y_p \\ (h_p - h_{\text{end}}) \cdot g(y, y_{\text{end}}, \sigma_{\text{end}}) + h_{\text{end}} & \text{if } y > y_{\text{end}} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

For density profiles with a **dip followed by a Gaussian falloff**, the end of the dip coincides with the start of the Gaussian falloff:

$$y_{\text{end}} = y_{\text{d2}} = 5.96 \text{ mm}$$

The equation for the density profiles with dip and Gaussian falloff:

$$n_{\text{dip+f}}(y) = \begin{cases} h_{\text{LWFA}} \cdot g(y, y_1, \sigma) & \text{if } y \leq y_1 \\ h_{\text{LWFA}} & \text{if } y_1 < y \leq y_2 \\ (h_{\text{LWFA}} - h_p) \cdot g(y, y_2, \sigma) + h_p & \text{if } y_2 < y \leq y_p \\ (h_{\text{LWFA}} - h_d) \cdot g(y, y_2, \sigma) + h_d & \text{if } y_2 < y \leq y_{\text{d1}} \\ (h_p - h_d) \cdot g(y, y_{\text{d2}}, \sigma_{\text{dip}}) + h_d & \text{if } y_{\text{d1}} < y \leq y_{\text{d2}} \\ (h_p - h_{\text{end}}) \cdot g(y, y_{\text{d2}}, \sigma_{\text{end}}) + h_{\text{end}} & \text{if } y > y_{\text{d2}} \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

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Dresden, 30th June 2025

Konrad Schlicke